

AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE ON *SHANKH BHASMA* AND ITS THERAPEUTIC ROLE
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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda emphasizes holistic management of women's health through *Dosha* balance and *Rasashastra* formulations. *Shankha Bhasma*, prepared from purified conch shells, is classified under *Sudha Varga* and possesses *Shita*, *Kshariya*, *Laghu*, *Kashaya*, and *Katu* properties. These confer *Pittashamana*, *Stambhana*, and *Agnideepana* actions, making it beneficial in *Yoni Rogas* (gynecological disorders) such as leucorrhoea, discharges, itching, pain, and menstrual disturbances. Classical texts describe 20 *Yonivyapads*, whose prevalence has increased due to stress, faulty diet, and neglect of *Dinacharya* and *Rajaswala Paricharya*. The *Lok-Purush Samya Siddhant* supports the therapeutic application of *Shankha Bhasma*, as the conch's *Trivarta* structure resembles that of the Yoni (vagina, cervix, uterus). Its *Kshariya* nature neutralizes inflammation and infections, while its *dosha*-balancing actions target *Rasa*, *Rakta*, and *Asthi dhatus*. This study integrates Ayurvedic theory and modern perspectives, highlighting *Shankha Bhasma* as a promising remedy for women's reproductive health requiring further clinical validation.

KEYWORDS: *Shankha Bhasma*; *Yoni Rogas*; *Yonivyapad*; *Ayurveda*; *Lok-Purush Samya Siddhant*; Women's health; *Rasashastra*.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda, the eternal science of life, provides an in-depth framework for understanding health and disease through its holistic and elemental approach. A prominent specialty within Ayurveda is *Rasa Shastra*, which involves the preparation of *Rasaushadhi*—herbo-mineral formulations known for their potency, efficacy, and rapid action. *Bhasma*, a category within *Rasaushadhi*, consists of incinerated minerals or metals and holds a vital role in therapeutic applications, particularly when precision and deep tissue action are required. One such important *bhasma* is *Shankha Bhasma*, prepared from conch shells (*Shankha*), rich in calcium and possessing unique properties. *Shankha* is classified under *Sudha Varga*, and when properly processed through *Shodhana* and *Marana*, it becomes therapeutically beneficial. *Shankha Bhasma* is attributed with *Shita*, *Laghu*, *Kshariya*, *Kashaya*, and *Katu* properties, which render it effective in *Pittashamana*, *Stambhana*, and *Agnideepana* actions.

Yoni Rogas refer to gynecological disorders and are classified as *Yonivyapad* in Ayurvedic literature. *Acharya Charaka* describes 20 types of *Yonivyapads*, which cover a wide range of conditions from infections to hormonal imbalances. Modern lifestyle changes, increased stress, poor diet, and neglect of *Dinacharya*, *Rutucharya*, and *Rajaswalaparicharya* have led to a sharp rise in such disorders. Ayurveda emphasizes maintaining the health of the *Yoni*—vagina and reproductive organs—through preventive and curative means. The concept of *Lok-Purush Samya Siddhant* from *Charaka Samhita* describes the microcosm–macrocosm theory—what exists in the universe (*Brahmanda*) exists in the individual (*Pinda*). The shape of *Shankha* is said to resemble that of the Yoni, particularly its three-fold structure (*Tri-avarta yoni*), giving rise to the therapeutic relevance of *Shankha Bhasma* in *Yoni Rogas*. This paper aims to explore this unique analogy and validate the efficacy of *Shankha Bhasma* in managing gynecological

disorders using Ayurvedic and modern scientific perspectives.

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

• Aim

To study the conceptual and therapeutic efficacy of *Shankha Bhasma* in the management of *Yoni Rogas* (gynecological disorders).

• Objectives

To explore the etiology and pathogenesis of *Yoni Rogas* in the context of modern stress and lifestyle.

To analyze the pharmacological and physicochemical properties of *Shankha Bhasma*.

To understand the application of *Lok Purush Samya Siddhant* in correlating the shape of *Shankha* with the *Yoni*.

To collect classical and contemporary evidence supporting

Shankha Bhasma in gynecological diseases.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Literature Review: Classical Ayurvedic texts such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridayam*, *Rasa Tarangini*, and *Rasaratna Samuccaya* were reviewed.
- Modern Sources: Standard gynecology references, published research articles, and journals were used to correlate findings.
- Visual and Anatomical Analysis: Comparative study of the anatomical structure of *Yoni and Shankha*.
- Preparation Details: Shodhana and Marana of *Shankha* for *Bhasma* preparation are referred from *Rasa* texts.

4. Role of Lifestyle and Modern Stress in *Yoni Rogas*

In the present era, women are increasingly exposed to psychological stress, irregular daily routines, erratic eating habits, and unhealthy lifestyles, all of which play a major role in the rising incidence of *Yoni Rogas*. The inability to follow classical Ayurvedic regimens such as *Dinacharya*, *Rutucharya*, *Rajaswala Paricharya*, and *Sutika Paricharya* results in *Doṣa* vitiation, especially of *Apāna Vāyu*, finally leading to various *Yonivyāpads*. *Āchārya Charaka* and *Vāgbhaṭa* have described twenty *Yonivyāpads*, broadly arising from four major etiological factors.

Mithyā Āhāra–Vihāra (faulty diet and lifestyle) is the foremost cause. Since *Rasa Dhātu* is the first nourished tissue and *Ārtava* is its *Upadhātu*, improper food and habits directly affect menstrual physiology. Practices such as overeating, incompatible or untimely food intake, processed diets, excessive caffeine, alcohol, smoking, and nutrient deficiency disturb *Agni*, aggravate *Vāta* and *Pitta*, and lead to *dysmenorrhea*, scanty bleeding, clot formation, insomnia, and cycle irregularity. Faulty lifestyle habits like suppression of natural urges, night awakening, ignoring menstrual care, improper exercise, and excessive sexual activity further derange *Apāna*

Vāyu, causing *Vātaja*, *Udāvartinī*, and *Pittaja Yoni Vyāpads*.

Bīja Doṣa (genetic factors) represents defects in the female gamete. Disturbance at the chromosomal or genetic level leads to *Beeja Bhāga Duṣṭi*, resulting in malformed organs, infertility, miscarriage, stillbirth, or congenital anomalies. Conditions like *Śandī Yoni Vyāpada* arise due to such inherent defects aggravated by *Vāta*.

Ārtava Duṣṭi manifests in three forms—*Dhātu-rūpī*, *Bīja-rūpī*, and *Rajasrava-rūpī Ārtava*. Hormonal imbalance, defective ovulation, and abnormal menstrual flow respectively cause infertility, *Aprajā*, *Aṣṭuja*, and *Arajaska*.

Lastly, *Daiva Kāraṇa* explains *Yoni Rogas* arising without evident physical cause, attributed to unseen karmic and spiritual factors. From the *Shankha–Yoni* concept, both share a hollow, delicate, and layered nature, making the *Yoni* highly sensitive to disturbances at physical, hormonal, genetic, and subtle levels.

5. Anatomy of *Yoni (Vagina)* in Ayurveda and Modern Science

According to *Āchārya Suśruta*, *Yoni* is one of the most vital structures of the female body and is described as having a *Shankhanābhi Ākr̥ti*, meaning a conch-like, spiral shape with three distinct *Avarthas* (structural divisions). The *Garbhashaya* (uterus) is situated in the third *Avartha*, highlighting its central role in conception, nourishment, and growth of the fetus. When the entire female reproductive system is understood under the concepts of *Yoni* and *Garbhashaya*, instead of restricting them merely to the vagina and uterus, the Ayurvedic explanation of anatomy and physiology becomes far more complete and clinically meaningful.

While describing *Srotasas* in the *Sushruta Samhitā*, *Āchārya Suśruta* states that they are innumerable but classifies the major ones into eleven pairs. Among these, the *Artavavaha Srotasa* holds special significance in gynecology. The concept of *Traya Avartha* of *Yoni* is unique to Ayurveda and closely parallels modern anatomical organization. The first *Avartha* corresponds to the vagina, extending from the vestibule to the external os. The second *Avartha* represents the cervix, situated between the external and internal os. The third *Avartha* is identified as the uterus, extending from the internal os up to the fundus, which houses the *Garbhashaya*.

Artava is described as both *Bahipushpa* (menstrual flow) and *Antahpushpa* (ovum). Hence, the uterus, ovaries, fallopian tubes, and vagina together constitute the *Artavavaha Srotasa*, responsible for menstruation, ovulation, and fertility. From the *Shankha* concept, the spiral, hollow, and layered nature of the *Yoni* resembles the structure of the conch shell, forming the basis for the

therapeutic application of Shankha Bhasma in Yoni Rogas.

From the modern anatomical view, the vagina is a fibromuscular canal extending from the cervix to the vestibule and functions as the passage for menstrual flow, the lower part of the birth canal, and the organ of copulation. The fornices surrounding the cervix, especially the posterior fornix near the recto-uterine pouch, are clinically important in Yoni disorders. Thus, the Ayurvedic and modern perspectives together strengthen the understanding of Yoni structure and its relevance in Yoni Roga Chikitsa.

6. Lok-Purush Samya Siddhant and Its Relevance

The Lok-Puruṣa Sāmya Siddhānta explains the fundamental concept that the human body is a miniature representation of the universe. This principle is not limited to spiritual realization such as *satyabuddhi* and *mokṣa*, but is extensively applied in Ayurveda to understand anatomy, physiology, pathology, and therapeutics through natural analogies. Āchārya Suśruta used this doctrine to interpret complex bodily structures and functions by observing similar patterns in nature.

In Aśmari Nidāna, Suśruta describes the movement of urine using the example of rivers flowing into the ocean, where nāḍīs transport urine from the intestines to the bladder.

पकाशयगतास्तत्र नाड्यो मूत्रवहास्तु माः ।

तपयन्ति सदा मूत्रं सरितः सागरं यथा ॥ (सु.नि. 3/21)

In Śira Śārīra, blood vessels originating from the nābhi are compared with irrigation channels and plant venules.

तासां प्रतानाः; तासां नाभिमूलं ततश्च

प्रसरन्त्यूर्ध्वमधः तिर्यक् च ॥ (सु.शा. 7/3)

Likewise, the internal channels of arteries are compared to the porous lotus stem in Dhamaṇī Śārīra.

यथा स्वभावात् खानि मृणालेषु बिसेषु च ।

धमनिनां तथा खानि रसो यत्र प्रपूर्यते ॥ (सु.शा. 9/10)

The universal functions of Visarga, Ādāna, and Vikṣepa, governed by Chandra, Sūrya, and Vāyu, correspond to Kapha, Pitta, and Vāta within the human body, maintaining physiological balance. This principle is also reflected in Yogya Abhyāsa, where surgical training was first practiced on plants and animals before human application.

From the Yoni Roga perspective, this Siddhānta gains special importance in explaining the therapeutic use of Shankha Bhasma. Shankha and Yoni exhibit structural resemblance, both being hollow, coiled, and tri-layered in nature. This anatomical similarity forms the basis for their functional correlation. Due to this resemblance, Shankha Bhasma effectively acts on Yoni disorders by

restoring structural integrity, regulating secretions, and maintaining local physiological balance. Thus, Lok-Puruṣa Sāmya Siddhānta provides a strong conceptual and therapeutic bridge between Shankha and Yoni in gynecological practice.

7. Shankha: Structure, Synonyms, Classification, and Importance Synonyms

Shankha is also known as *Dakshinavarta Shankha* in classical texts, referring to the conch with a right-sided spiral that holds high medicinal and ritual significance.

Structure

Shankha is characterized by its white, glossy outer surface and a spirally coiled inner structure. It is the hard, calcareous external shell of marine mollusks. Chemically, it is composed mainly of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) arranged in the form of aragonite crystals. After systematic purification and incineration, the dense and layered structure of Shankha is converted into a fine, bioavailable form rich in absorbable calcium, making it suitable for therapeutic use.

Classification

Shankha is classified under drugs of marine animal origin and included in the Sudha Varga group as per Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals due to its alkaline and calcium-dominant nature.

Source

Shankha is collected from sea beds and coastal regions, especially from areas rich in marine biodiversity. Only well-formed, unbroken, and naturally spiraled conch shells are selected for medicinal preparation.

Pharmaceutical Processing

Shankha Bhasma is prepared through classical Ayurvedic procedures such as Shodhana (purification) and Marana (incineration). These processes involve repeated heating, herbal levigation, and controlled calcination, which remove physical and chemical impurities and convert the raw shell into a safe, detoxified, and therapeutically potent formulation. During this transformation, biochemical changes including oxidation-reduction reactions take place, along with the integration of herbal elements that enhance trace mineral content and improve intestinal absorption.

Importance in Yoni Roga

In the context of Yoni Roga, Shankha Bhasma is valued for its Kshariya, Stambhana, and Pittashamana actions. It helps regulate abnormal vaginal discharges, reduces excessive secretions, pacifies inflammatory conditions, and supports tissue stability. Its rich calcium content further aids in strengthening local cellular structures and maintaining physiological balance. Proper standardization of Shankha Bhasma through classical and modern parameters is essential to ensure its safety, purity, and clinical effectiveness.

8. Shankha Bhasma: Preparation and Properties

Shankha Bhasma is an important herbo-mineral formulation widely used in Ayurveda, especially in disorders of the gastrointestinal and female reproductive systems. The preparation of Shankha Bhasma involves two major pharmaceutical steps—Shodhana (purification) and Marana (incineration). During Shodhana, the conch shell is subjected to Swedana (boiling) in Nimbu Swarasa (lemon juice) using a Dolayantra, which helps in removing physical and chemical impurities while enhancing its therapeutic potential. In the Marana process, the purified Shankha is triturated with Kumari Swarasa (Aloe vera juice) and incinerated at around 700°C, converting it into a fine, bio-assimilable ash.

Shankha Bhasma is endowed with Deepana and Pachana properties, which strengthen digestive fire and correct metabolism. It also acts as Grahani-balya, improving intestinal strength, and has Stambhana action that helps control excessive discharges. Its Pittashamana effect makes it highly effective in conditions associated with acidity and burning sensations. The drug is described as having Sheeta, Kshariya, Laghu, Katu, and Kashaya qualities, and it primarily acts on Rasa, Rakta, and Asthi Dhatus.

From the Yoni Roga perspective, the concept of Kshariya is highly significant. The interaction of Amla (acidic) and Kshara (alkaline) properties results in a Madhura (neutralizing) effect, which is beneficial in reducing inflammation, controlling infections, and restoring the normal vaginal environment. This makes Shankha Bhasma useful in conditions such as Shweta Pradara (leucorrhoea), vaginal itching, abnormal discharges, painful menstruation, and infectious Yoni Rogas.

Therapeutically, it is also indicated in Ajirna, Grahani, Amlapitta, chronic diarrhea, colic pain, hepatosplenomegaly, and certain toxic conditions. The calcium content of Shankha Bhasma further supports cellular stability, neuromuscular function, and enzymatic activity, making it structurally strong and therapeutically effective in both systemic and gynecological disorders.

Shankha Bhasma in Yoni Roga Indications (Yoni Roga Prayoga)

Shankha Bhasma is therapeutically useful in the following gynecological disorders.

- Shweta Pradara (Leucorrhoea)
- Yoni Kandu (Vaginal itching)
- Yonigata Srava (Abnormal vaginal discharge)
- Kashtartava (Painful menstruation)
- Yonigata Daha (Burning sensation)
- Yonigata Sankramana (Infections)
- Amlapitta-janya Yoni Vikara (Acidic pH-related vaginal disorders)

Its Stambhana and Pittashamana properties make it especially effective in excessive discharges and

inflammatory vaginal conditions.

Mode of Action (Karma in Yoni Roga) Shankha Bhasma acts primarily through.

- Kshariya Guna – Helps neutralize excessive vaginal acidity and maintains normal vaginal pH.
 - Stambhana Karma – Controls excessive vaginal secretions and discharge.
 - Pittashamana Karma – Reduces burning, redness, and inflammatory changes.
 - Agnideepana and Pachana – Corrects systemic digestive impairment, which is an important underlying cause in recurrent Yoni Rogas.
 - Calcium Action – Strengthens epithelial tissue, supports cellular stability, and improves local healing.
- Thus, it works both locally on Yoni and systemically through Agni and Dosha balance.

Dose (Matra)

- 125 mg to 250 mg, once or twice daily
- Always administered under medical supervision

Anupana (Adjuvant)

Depending on the Dosha involvement.

- Honey (Madhu) – In Kapha-dominant Shweta Pradara
- Lodhra Kashaya / Tandulodaka – In excessive discharge
- Aloe vera juice – In Pitta-dominant burning and inflammation
- Buttermilk (Takra) – In recurrent infections with Grahani involvement

9. DISCUSSION

The present study highlights the growing impact of modern lifestyle factors, psychological stress, and disturbed daily regimens on the increasing prevalence of Yoni Rogas. Irregular dietary practices, excessive caffeine intake, addictions, night awakening, and neglect of menstrual hygiene directly vitiate Agni, Rasa Dhātu, and Apāna Vāyu, leading to abnormalities in Ārtava and manifestation of various Yonivyāpads. Genetic factors (Bīja Doṣa), hormonal disturbances (Ārtava Duṣṭi), and unseen influences (Daiva Kāraṇa) further complicate the etiopathogenesis of gynecological disorders.

The Ayurvedic anatomical concept of Yoni as Shankhanābhi Ākṛti, with three Avarthas, closely correlates with modern understanding of the vagina, cervix, and uterus, reinforcing the holistic view of the female reproductive system. The application of Lok–Puruṣa Sāmya Siddhānta establishes a conceptual bridge between the structural similarity of Shankha and Yoni, providing a strong theoretical basis for the gynecological use of Shankha Bhasma.

Pharmacologically, Shankha Bhasma exhibits Kṣāriya, Stambhana, Pittashamana, and Agnideepana actions. Its

role in regulating vaginal pH, reducing inflammation, controlling discharge, and improving epithelial strength through its calcium content makes it highly effective in Shweta Pradara, Yoni Kandu, Kashtartava, and infectious Yoni disorders. Thus, Shankha Bhasma offers both systemic correction and local therapeutic benefits in Yoni Rogas.

10. CONCLUSION

Yoni Rogas are multifactorial disorders deeply influenced by modern lifestyle, stress, dietary irregularities, genetic factors, hormonal disturbances, and subtle karmic influences. The Ayurvedic description of Yoni as Shankhanābhi Ākr̥ti and the application of Lok–Puruṣa Sāmya Siddhānta provide a strong anatomical and therapeutic rationale for the use of Shankha Bhasma. Its Kṣāriya, Stambhana, Pittashamana, and calcium-rich properties effectively address both the local and systemic components of Yoni Rogas. When prepared and administered properly, Shankha Bhasma serves as a safe, rational, and effective therapeutic agent in gynecological practice.

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